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Review Article

From Fields to Climate Pathways: Climate-Smart Agriculture in Indian and Global Contexts

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ABSTRACT

Agriculture is vulnerable and a contributor to climate change. Climate-smart Agriculture (CSA) offers a strategic approach to achieve productivity, adaptation and mitigation goals. Through qualitative data analysis approach, this review includes basic literature reviews, policy and content analysis to understand the concept of climate change, its impact on agriculture, climate-smart agriculture and various initiatives taken by India and other countries to address the issue. Our review reveal that many countries are making efforts to achieve climate-smart agriculture goal, but major implementation gap persist. Case studies highlight major initiatives take by countries but there is always a need for a strategic approach. Globally, adaptation of CSA is uneven. Through this review, we summarise that policy framework for CSA exists in India and countries. However, in both cases, decentralised planning to overcome implementation barrier and capacity-building trainings should be in place for addressing information gap.

INTRODUCTION

A phenomenon of long-term shifts in weather patterns of a particular place (or entire globe) is known as climate change. Climate change influences by natural factors anthropogenic activities such as deforestation, maximum fertilizer usage or combustion of fossil fuel (Nunes, 2023; Khan, 2025; Sen et al., 2025). This uncertain shift in weather pattern affects human

survival and farming (Abdelmordy et al., 2022; Upadhyay, 2015). Another primary contributor to this climate change crises is the increasing concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere, which notably escalates global warming (Kabato et al., 2025). As per UNEP, global greenhouse gas emission reached 57.1 gigatonnes.

Climate change significantly poses threatened on food production and its security, water, crops and other things, by combining various natural

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phenomenon including changing rainfall patterns, raising drought conditions and excessive temperature (Mirzabaev et al., 2022; Muluneh, 2021, Nunes, 2023). Agriculture being the backbone of India, contributing about 18.3% to the India's Gross Domestic Production (GDP), providing about 42.3 percent livelihood to the farmer community of India (Mancosu et al., 2015; Gulati & Juneja, 2022). Agriculture is a victim and

contributor to a paramount amount of Greenhouse gases (Wing et al., 2021). Under the warming scenario, it is estimated climate change will reduce crop production globally by 3-12% by mid-century and 11-25% by the end of the century (Abramoff et al., 2023).

Climate change has an impact on various elements, including:

Aspects/ Components of Agriculture	Role in agriculture	Impact of Climate Change	References
Water Management	Water is the backbone of agriculture sector. The irrigation sector consumes the maximum fresh water. To achieve the performance, developing countries spent maximum fresh water as compared to developed countries	Changes in water cycle, when it increases atmospheric temperature, effects both river runoff and groundwater. Although the land for crop production has decreased but the requirement and demand of water resources in agriculture sector has doubled since past decades, increases competition for water utilising among other sectors.	Mancosu et al., 2015; Goap et al., 2018; Ridoutt et al., 2021; Abdelmordy et al., 2022
Crop production system	Improving agriculture sector by adapting the negative effects of climate change by ensuring food security and improve livelihood directly the main objective of improving crop production system in agriculture.	Climate change is critical for food security. During the growing periods, extreme weather scenarios and droughts severely effect flora and fauna of a habitat. Climate changes led to fluctuations in planting dates, finding new locations, diversification of crops and intercropping. However, the successes or failure of crop completely depends on whether events.	Abdelmordy et al., 2022; Omokanye et al., 2022; Wakweya, 2025; Mahankuda & Tiwari, 2024
Soil Management	Land helps control atmospheric gases and water, and it supplies nutrients and water that plants' roots can absorb. The essential functions that the soil offers to support plant growth enhance the health of the plants.	A decrease in rainfall and increase in evaporation caused by global warming events reduce the moisturiser of soil required for plant growth. Fluctuation in soil structure impacts the absorption and transmission of water, minerals and carbon.	Romero-Ruiz et al., 2018; Lobell et al., 2008
Fisheries and aquaculture	Fisheries and aquaculture sector is responsible for generating employment opportunity for about 660.82 million people and women participation in agriculture sector.	Hydrological changes widely impact pH, salinity, temperature and ecosystem of aquaculture productivity and rises risks.	Macusi et al., 2023; FAO, 2006; Hal et al., 2023

Livestock	The livestock sector is a substantial contributor to climate change, emitting large amounts of N ₂ O, CH ₄ , and CO ₂ .	Grazing systems are predicted to be the most affected by high greenhouse gas emissions since they are heavily dependent on the natural resource base and climatic conditions and have limited adaptability. The adverse climatic shifts exacerbates water scarcity, heat stress on livestock and decline food crop production.	Abdelmordy et al., 2022; Henry et al., 2018; Laible et al., 2015
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MATERIALS AND METHODS:

By using qualitative data analysis approach, this review includes basic literature reviews, policy and content analysis to understand the concept of climate change, its impact on agriculture, climate-smart agriculture and various initiatives taken by India and other countries to address the issue. A literature review is foundation of the study. The stages of literature review include collecting initiatives taken by Indian government to address climate change issue, comparing global initiatives for Indian agriculture to adopt best practice and analysing the data for future recommendation. The data collection includes extensive literature review to gather information and data from existing reviews. This review identifies best practices that can be inculcated to ensure climate-smart agriculture.

Climate-Smart agriculture:

Eriksen et al stated that as similar to policymakers, many farmers believe that deforestation is a major contributor to climate change. However, this definition of the problem reflects an outlook in which people have a rigid moral relationship with nature, with unpredictable weather patterns being the result of "immoral" or "greedy" behaviour that interrupts the relationship between humans and resources.

To tackle 1.5°C shift, climate-smart agriculture (CSA) strategies are essential. CSA potential approaches for crop production improvement and resource management by including technological, institutional and community support. According to Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), agriculture that increases productivity and incomes while addressing sustainability, enhances adaptation, minimising greenhouse gas (mitigation) emission where possible, and address achievement of national food security and development goals (FAO 2018).

CSA is a roadmap to increase crop productivity and generate income while addressing sustainability. CSA innovations which provides a comprehensive framework for promoting higher crop production, soil retention, enhance nutrient use efficiency and availability, technologies involves precision agriculture, crop-rotation, agroforestry, biochar application, regenerative agriculture (Lehmann et al., 2021; Quandt et al., 2023; Kabato et al., 2025; Yang et al., 2024; Mishra et al., 2022).

According to Sapkota et al., CSA is practice which includes conservation agriculture techniques like alternative crop production techniques, minimum tillage, irrigation management and nutrient rich crop production to ensure food security, greenhouse gas reduction, and water management. According to Lipper and Zilberman (2018) initially, the CSA concept understood to achieve

three major goals: sustainably increasing food security, building resilience to climate change, and minimising greenhouse gas emissions. Due to a lack of a clear strategy, originating in differing interpretations and dispute. Over time, a methodology created, underlining the importance of evidence-based assessments, a supportive policy environment, and coordinated collaborations. Mullar defines CSA as a sustainable framework that can boost crop productivity and expenditure by using adaptation approaches while boosting climate resilience and minimizing greenhouse gas emissions. World Bank Group defines CSA as “an integrated

approach to managing food-producing landscapes” that underscores global challenges such as food security and climate change.

Pillars of CSA:

CSA support rural communities to enhance food security and accessibility to technologies supporting knowledge which ultimately gain farmers' confidence. The aim to address triple wins (i) increasing agriculture production (ii) minimising GHG emission (iii) climate-change resilience (Pedersen, 2024).

CSA Pillar	Components	Strategies / practice	Contribution
Productivity	Sustainability of food production and security Pathway of food production to security and nutrition	Improve crop varieties by enhancing drought and animal heat tolerance, resistant Precision farming including using modern technologies including AI, IoT, drones, robotics (Mgendi, 2024). Mechanization, integration of low-emission tools Efficient drip irrigation and solar pump	Increase crop yields under climate stress, improve resources efficiency Reduce labor Efficient water management and crop health, food accessibility (Chandra et al., 2017)
Adaptation	Short-term adaptation Long term adaptation	Agroforestry, focusing on trees, crops and livestock Rainwater harvesting, mulching Crop diversification Climate-informed extension and training	Erosion control Soil efficiency, delayed drought Improve soil fertility Farmer capacity building for real-time decision-making practices
Mitigation	Short-term GHG emission estimates Estimate trends Monitoring reporting & verification (MRV) Finance & market mechanisms	Manure management and feeding livestock, herd management, capture biogas and reduce CH4 emission reduce tillage and residue retention increase soil C, reduces CO2 loss Biochar application	Reduce GHGs methane Long-term soil carbon sequestration Ensure food security Wijk et al., 2020

Climate-smart agriculture policies:

India					
Policy/ Initiative	Year	Implementing Bodies	Focus Area	Key Strategies	Progress

National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture (NMSA)	2012	Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers' Welfare (GoI); state agri departments.	Rainfed area development; efficient utilization of natural resources using community-based approach; livelihood diversification; nutrient management	Promote composite farming including crops, livestock, fishery and plantation; encourage resource conservation strategies, crop rotation and agroforestry to support mitigate practices; adopt water management strategies including rainwater harvesting, micro irrigation; focus on soil testing, minimal usage of fertilizers and water holding capacity; utilizing ICT tools and maintain database for knowledge sharing; capacity-building trainings	Around 30,690,000 hectares area brought under micro irrigation. 342,000 hectares brought under Integrated Farming System. Provided soil health card to the farmer community to provide information on the status of soil nutrient Capacity-building on appropriate supply of fertilizers
National Innovations in Climate Resilient Agriculture (NICRA)	2011	Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR, Ministry of Agri) with state research institutes	Adaptation and mitigation; Technologies demonstration; disaster management; efficient resources utilization	identification of most vulnerable districts/regions, (ii) expand crop varieties and management practices for adaptation and mitigation, (iii) assessing climate change impacts on livestock, fisheries and poultry and identifying adaptation strategies.	16,958 training programs nation-wide, covering 5,14,816 stakeholders enable wider adoption of climate resilient technologies and increase in yields, Custom hiring centers (CHCs) in around 121 villages to ensure availability of farm implements for timely operations. ¹
Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchayee Yojana – “Per Drop More Crop”	2015	Ministry of Agriculture & FW (GOI) in partnership with state irrigation boards	micro-irrigation, organic farming, cooperative society targeting	Supporting for installation of micro irrigation system is limited to five hectares per beneficiary	Between FY16 and FY21, 95.58 lakh hectares were covered, with a rise in gross cropped area (GCA) from 49.3 to 55% and irrigation intensity from 144.2 to 154.5%.

¹ <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleaseFramePage.aspx?PRID=1743354>

			Primary Agricultural Credit Societies (PACS)		Established more than 9,000 new PACS, dairy, and fishing cooperatives. Around 35,293 PACS serve as Pradhan Mantri Kisan Samridhhi Kendras (PMKSK), and 1,723 micro-ATMs have been given to improve access to financial services in rural areas.
Paramparagat Krishi Vikas Yojana (Organic Farming)	2015	Ministry of Agriculture & FW (GOI) via state governments	soil health, soil Health Management (SHM)	adopting eco-friendly, low- cost technologies, organic farming, experts from public agricultural research system	Around 14.99 lakh hectares turned into organic farming, 52289 clusters developed involving 25.30 lakh farmers. Under the scheme, 8 states developed their organic products brands.
PM Kisan Urja Suraksha evam Utthaan Mahabhayan (PM-KUSUM)	2019	Ministry of New and Renewable Energy (MNRE)	Water and energy security, de-dieselisation of the farm sector	setting up of 10,000 MW of Decentralized Ground/Stilt Mounted Solar Power Plants on barren/fallow/pasture/marshy/ cultivable land of farmers.	Installation of 14 lakh stand-alone solar pumps in off-grid locations. Solarisation of 35 lakh grid-connected agriculture pumps can be achieved through two methods: individual pump solarisation and feeder level solarisation.
Global					
Adaptation for Smallholder Agriculture Programme (ASAP)	2012	IFAD (International Fund for Agri Development)	Climate finance, livelihood, capacity-building, mitigate GHG, climate driven food insecurity	The flagship program has been implemented in 3 phrases of intervention focused on: -Support in ensuring climate resilient practices and mitigate GHG emissions -Aimed in providing technical support by resource mobilization and capacity-building -Putting expertise for rural communities and putting best stories from phrase 1 and 2	Implemented in 43 countries to support 8 million small-scale farmers. mitigate about 60 million tons of carbon dioxide and enhances climate resilient practices on 1 million hectares of land

Global Agriculture and Food Security Program (GAFSP)	2010	World Bank-led trust fund (with AfDB, ADB, AIIB, FAO, etc)	Access to Finance Climate Change Fragility Gender Inclusive Business Jobs and Income Nutrition	Provide grants to low-income countries; finance solutions and concessional funding to support smallholder farmers; addressing food loss; developing tools for GHG reduction and cost-saving techniques; encourage climate-smart crop production	19.2 million people benefited from the public sector projects, reached out to 42% women, 4.5 million people have health food and diverse diet.
Global Alliance for Climate-Smart Agriculture (GACSA)	2014	FAO (UN) facilitates; includes 14 governments, 30+ organizations (private, civil society).	Climate-smart agriculture; food security and nutrition; climate resilient	integrated knowledge-intensive approach for encourage collaborative CSA strategies through initiatives, engagement and programs; knowledge generation and capacity-building	Recognizes success through partnership for sensitizing 500+ million farmers.
World Bank Climate-Smart Agriculture Programs	2016–present	World Bank (with national governments)	Food security; low GHG emission; climate finance	Providing financial support to countries; repurpose of existing projects to include CSA standards	disseminating knowledge and identifying possibilities on food security. Execution of analytics into transformative actions by providing financing and advice Collaborations and global partnership for private sector financing

Per Drop More Crop Case study:

In many semi-arid regions of India, **sudden rainfall** and **groundwater depletion** affect crop production. Traditional flood irrigation approach for wastes water often lacks cope with unpredictable climate-change patterns. Increasing demand for water in agriculture “requires

innovative solutions”. Drip, sprinkler irrigation directly addresses these challenges: it delivers required quantity water to plant roots, minimize overuse, waterlogging and crop stress. By matching irrigation to soil, crop, and terrain conditions, drip techniques minimize water scarcity, enhance nutrient uptake and support in stabilize yields under climatic change.

As part of the implementation of program "Per Drop More Crop", the aim was to reduce water utilisation and building drought resilience in smallholder systems. To collect baseline data, **field studies** on soil type, water availability, crop variety, and agro-climatic parts to design tailored drip systems. In practice, this meant installing drip tubing and releases for key crops (onion, mango, banana, etc.) and scheduling irrigation properly. The support was equipped in framework designing, farmer capacity-building training, and after-sales service to ensure systems are properly manager. A demonstration trial on onion production in the Tapi River basin (Maharashtra) comparing drip vs. conventional irrigation was also curated. This approach quantified water savings and yield effects. The implementation framework combined **technology deployment** (micro-irrigation hardware), **capacity-building** (training, extension bus), and **value-chain support** (market linkages, standards).

The intervention has shown substantial change. It was reported onion cultivation saved 1200 liters of water. More than 5 lakh farmers, out of which the participation of 50000 women in the India micro-irrigation market. Notably, a positive effect on food security was also estimated.

Uganda, FAO Case study:

Agriculture is backbone for Uganda's economic. It is estimated that 66 percent depend on agriculture, with 80 percent of the rural community. Only 1% of farming is irrigated, and around 96% of farming is dependent on rain. Ugandan agriculture faces multiple challenges. First, agriculture households lack the resources to adapt climate-smart practices. Their own most farmers have limited access to weather information, training or climate-smart technologies (e.g. drought-tolerant seeds, water-harvesting systems and improved livestock breeds). The agriculture infrastructure is fragile

including, crop irrigation, storage and mobilize remain under-developed. Many communities are land-constrained (especially for women, youth and landless households) push backwards investment for long period (Asma, 2023). Women lack accessibility to inputs and decision-making, this makes gender equity both, a barrier and a priority.

As an integrated implementation part, FAO assisted with tools and technical guidance, UNDP offered adaptation planning expertise. On of the objective also to assist district governments to translate the national agricultural program. As a core intervention part, SCALA held two -week workshops on Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV) tool for agriculture and land use. Apart from ths, tge program focused on engaging private sector abd agribusiness. Many cattle- corridor districts were engaged in developing their local development policies. The key areas included multi-level partnership including 60+ multi-sector stakeholders, district, local government, planners, experts and private ensured adaptation plans are locally acceptable and stakeholders are ready to integrate. Secondly, the training and capacity building focused on highlighting women's participation cannot be ignored. Lastly, the idea was to avoid duplicity of work, SCALA supported in aligning Uganda's NAP, NDC and district planning process. Currently, the program has overcome the finance gaps.

In conclusion, Uganda's SCALA case demonstrates transformation through coordinated policy support, capacity building and community engagement can bring impact under climate stress. The cattle-corridor pilot is establishing a blueprint: systems assessments inform investment plans, gender- and context-appropriate CSA practices are promoted, and national targets are embedded in local budgets. These integrated interventions are

expected to improve yields and resilience in the long run.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION:

While India is standing to its critical juncture of economic development, the country is making continuous efforts dedicated to CSA strategies through their implementation scope and vary. To address the climate change issue, Government of India introduced National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC). The plan consists of eight National Mission focused on climate change, adaptation and mitigation, energy efficiency and natural resource conservation. As a key initiative under the NAPCC, National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture (NMSA) focuses on improving livestock, crop seeds, fish culture, water conservation, pest management, accessibility to information and livelihood diversification. Whereas National Initiative on Climate Resilient Agriculture, NICRA prioritized rainfed farming, resources management and livestock system. Another flagship program, such as Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchayee Yojana (PMKSY), “Per Drop-More Crop” have widely expanded micro-irrigation. During 2019-21, about 16 lakh farmers were benefited and 20.39 lakh hectare land has been covered under the scheme. FAO’s SHARP+ tool for district development plans embedding CSA. FAO along with development agencies have supported CSA globally through national adaptation plan. These all-global efforts including for achieving CSA goals have shown that the framework of a mix strategy including top-down and bottom-up plays emphasis for CSA framework. These efforts represent global CSA goals. As per World Bank’s “triple win” approach of productivity, climate resilience adaptation and lower emission, countries are continuously making efforts to

maintain equilibrium (World Bank, 2024; Jumiyati, 2024).

Our review reveal that many countries are making efforts to achieve climate-smart agriculture goal, but major implementation gap persist. The above-mentioned case studies highlight major initiatives take by countries but there are always a need for a strategic approach. Globally, adaptation of CSA is uneven. Taking lessons from Uganda’s case study, district government still reported limited budget for implementation process. Weak institutions have become a common barrier across countries.

Due to resource scarcity, lack of capacity building trainings, and weak institutions, Indian states struggle to implement CSA state plans. India's efforts towards adoption of drip/sprinklers have certainly boost water conservation and increased crop production in semi-arid areas, but many smallholders still rely on flood irrigation due to high upfront costs. Similarly, while ICT-based technologies (weather forecasts, market apps) are becoming more accessible, but rural farmers still have limited access.

There are existing institutional gaps. Due to lack of decentralized planning, most of the projects often face insufficient extension resource person, poor department coordination and also lack of proper local tracking system. There is a requirement for NGOs and other grassroots agencies to focus on capacity-building for CSA. As per Barooah et al, both men and women involve in farming activities but gender different persist men holds responsibility of managing agricultural inputs like equipment, fertilisers, pesticides, and transportation to markets, while women are responsible for manual labour such as weeding, fodder collection, and crop maintenance without specialised equipment. Studies reveals that farmers are widely focus on including balanced fertilisers as women’s consistence involvement in

husbandry they play crucial role in preparing this natural fertilizer. To enable women farmers to increase agricultural production and improve CSA practices, the burden of household work must be minimized. Women are responsible for domestic tasks, animal husbandry, and field management due to men's decreasing involvement in household chaos (Barooah et al., 2023).

Through this review, we summarise that policy framework for CSA exists in India and countries. However, in both cases, decentralised planning to overcome implementation barrier and capacity-building trainings should be in place for addressing information gap. Bottlenecks relate to implementation include limited budget, lack of accessibility of technologies, institutional limitations at the subnational level. It is important to provide training to local stakeholders for technology improvement and adoption of CSA. Farmer Field Schools and farmer cooperatives have emerged as viable co-learning and demonstration settings. Finally, any effective CSA endeavour must be inclusive: integrating gender (via SHGs, land rights, and participatory planning) and youth participation will increase impact and equity.

Recommendation:

India is an agrarian economy and climate change has its direct effect on the agriculture where climate smart agriculture will act as a shield from climatic effects. What is recommended is **decentralized planning** through which we can strengthen the local governance for effective implementation of CSA policies and programs. Any planning done to resist climate change should have **inclusive approach** ensuring it is not increasing gender and income gap. Rather the policy and implementation ensure that participation from diverse socio-economic group

make the CSA initiatives more inclusive be it access to resources, training and decision-making.

Along with **strengthening local institution** we should consider exclusive focus on farmers focused organizations like FPOs and **capacity building** of local stakeholders such as farmers, extension workers to equip them with CSA based approach and knowledge which will support the CSA adoption. This can be well executed through common learning platform such as **farm schools** oriented completely on the lines of field learning.

One of the major challenges in Indian agriculture is traditional practice as maximum people who are practicing farming doesn't possess basic education to be able to use the advance technology. India agriculture is not mechanized but, time is changing the technology is finding its way to rural India. With the concept of CSA the importance of technology is evident and among the many recommendation one which is very crucial to navigate climate change impact on agriculture is **accessibility of technology** which are climate-resilient and can support farmers in agriculture be it irrigation system, or identifying crop variety, or work as a weather forecasting or soil tester even for small farmers as India has more small and marginal farmers as compared to big farmers.

Any **policy framework** of climate smart agriculture should consider sustainable practices and a robust well-designed **monitoring and evaluation** systems to track progress, identify gaps, and inform policy and program improvements.

CONCLUSION:

Climate change poses significant threats to agricultural productivity, food security, and sustainability. Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) offers a promising approach to address these

challenges by integrating adaptation, mitigation, and productivity enhancement strategies. India and other countries have initiated various policies and programs to promote CSA, but implementation gaps and institutional barriers persist.

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